

vrfvnt,vrfmclz;on/ 'bcsmf&yf vwmjyiu vrjrpftMum;wGf clefyt/vm;
 aelluaom ig;yduav;rs;onf ulelawm\ upm;azmrsm; jzpcMuon/ awmrðavmif
 jyðæmuif aeylususwGf xluay:vmluaom ywwp m yGf;sm;onf pmq\ tm[m&
 jzpcbn/ aemucðawm ta&;uif uGf;pywGf eð&ÿG ðæaom ayguÿifonf pmq\zð
 awmum;awmifum; jzpcbn/ anmiðy&ð tkwð&wGf;Muðrs iif, &aom a&at;onf
 ulelawmftwGf oðvma&csrf jzpcbnf[kpmq\ul\ lwlfolloboullwifjyðbnf

auşvuðawm&ð ywDef;usiü awð&? jri&? Mum;&? çpm;&aom taMumifjicif
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 usvmaom apwemonfvnf; oN uAsmwllul &omxtapon/ auşawmo?
 auşawmom;wllul çpçifaom? av;pm;aom? jrwe\ aom? Muifæaom apwemyif
 jzpcbn/ zEð&mwGfvnf; rifoðPN uAsmwllul taMumifoih t½çp m;wllubm
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 yom' *IPfajrmubonf[kqE\bn/ xlyif tolvnfomon/ at;jron/ ES\Hom;rs
 vGfvGjrnfvmaom tolygonf[kqE\bn/ xllumi hpmq\ uAsmwllulzwrðmrbl
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2? 1/ rifoðPN auşawmuAsmrsm;rs &mobbnð

auşvuðawm&ð &mobbnðtvşulvnf; pmq\rif oðPiu cgaEçqefawmh vçf;rw, f
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 opÿifvðrS tprçfa&mi lvpDu? tOga&mi lvpDupçuðom op&çur sm; auyllul aMumi fi, f
 onf rðçtjçrs;ul rðvluçzçoubo\ avayðv½;xlwGf csmvnywfvnf; vnium
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- qef;pcgaEG
- omwaygif;r\ nçanmi fau
- ajyajya&m½k
- jrta&; a&ð&;vkv\
- &wkt nD
- ajro\ oulvha&m&ç&çul\
- yvlyvmvðvmvm
- onçg "avh
- aEçt ul av½;taOðawmð
- aulauçDef;Olluf
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xlyif awmply, yefav;rsn;onf a0a0qmqm ztyG haeluon/ xlyef uav;rsn;
onf &eloi f xkom avjynfxlvGf c&ubh omomuav;ES fit wl vG hvmyluh zDqH
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 on/ obmO]tv]sonf wi]w, bu]b]y]if x]]t]o]d]t]j]ri]w]] on]v]n]f, wi]w, f]v]S
 ayon/ v]]w]]on]f r]e]i]b]b]m]O]\ t]v]E]S f]]u]i]f]]u]v]G]f v]]w]]on]f , k]v]e]r]h]o]m]o]b]m]O]]
 a&mu]]U&r]n]u]] pmq]h]i]f]o]D]P]bnf uav;i , f]]w]]\ obmO]q]e]a]om t]o]d]t]j]ri]w]]z]ih
 E]]f , O]f]um c]o]u]s;a&];z]]x]m;on/

2? 3/ ri]f]o]D]P]Na]u]s]aw]mu]A]s]r]m]r]S]v]i , h]a]r]m]i]f , f]]w]]\ t]c]p]h]a&];

Al'bmom jref]m]v]r]e]f]]w]]\ , O]a]u]s]r]i]'a]v]k]h]o]w]p]&]y]E]S]h]t]w]l] t]c]p]h]a&];u]]v]n]f ajAmo]]
 u]A]s]m]E]S]h]O]g]w]G]f]c]e]f]u]A]s]m]w]]u] aw]G]E]]f]on/

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 a' :a&]]r] O]a&]]c]r]f]i , f]]w]]
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 x]b]w]e]f]]U]b]v]y]g]b]d []k]a&];z]]x]m

ausawma' orsm;u &S]j]y]k]v]G]f &S]h]a]v]m]i]f]v]s]h]]uon/ &S]h]a]v]m]i]f]v]s]h]]m]w]G]f
 &S]j]y]k]r]n]h]a]r]m]i] &S]h]a]v]m]i]f]u]]t]O]w]f]t]p]m;? u]]U]]k]w]e]f]q]m] t]p]h]q]i]f] j]r]i]f]ay:]w]i]f]um] a&]]x]D]r]m;
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